

Ἥφαιστος : cognate with ἠπίολος, ἠπίᾰλος/ἐπίαλος and ἐφῖᾰλτης/ ἐπιάλτης , from a root-meaning “fire; burning”, possibly non-IE

Alexandru Gheorghiu

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Back in late 2022, I got the idea that Ancient Greek Ἥφαιστος : Hēphaistos (Doric Ἄφαιστος : Hāphaistos ; Aeolic Ἄφαιστος : Āphaistos) is cognate with Ancient Greek ἠπίᾰλος (ēpíālos), ἐπίαλος (epíālos) (“ague, fever; nightmare”), ἐφῖᾰλτης (ep̄hīältēs), ἐπιάλτης (epiältēs) (“nightmare”), ἠπίολος (ēpíolos) (“moth”).

The idea was/is that Ἥφαιστος and its variants meant “Fiery/Burning”, with the words meaning “fever, ague, nightmare” deriving from the meaning “fever”, in turn from “burning; fiery”. The moth word ἠπίολος (ēpíolos) in this scenario comes from the moth being attracted to flame, and because moths are attracted to flame, they were believed by many to cause fevers. Compare Lithuanian drugys (“fever, moth”) and Albanian ethe / hethe (“fever”) vis-a-vis Albanian ethëzë/ethezë (“moth”): these Albanian words are from Proto-Albanian *aida(s), from Proto-Indo-European *h₂eidh-o- (“burning fire”), and cognate to Ancient Greek αἶθος (aîthos, “burning, fire”), Old English *ád* (“funeral pyre”), Old Saxon *ēd* (“firebrand”) et al.

Another word for “ague, fever” in Ancient Greek is πῦρετός (“fever, heat”) from πῦρ (pûr) (“fire; lightning; a fever”).

Hephaistos was the god of fire, smithwork, metallurgy, volcanoes and artisans.

I recall that I first published this Hephaestus etymology of mine in January of 2023 in a session for one of Peter S. Piispanen’s drafts; I began discussing this Hephaestus etymology of mine because the discussion went

towards either Proto-Uralic *koje “dawn”/Proto-Uralic *kaja (“sun, dawn; to dawn”) or towards Proto-Uralic *koje (“male”), which I was saying could all be cognate with Proto-Uralic *käjä “moth”, because all these words could be from an older meaning “burning, fiery”, with the “male” word included as well since, for example, in the Chinese Yang-Yin system, male is Yang: fiery and identified with the sun.

I had intended to publish all that work soon in a paper of mine, but I had mostly forgotten, and many other things came up.

Previously, I had thought (and written in a notebook of mine in 2021/2022, but never published) that Hephaistos was cognate with Phaistos, the name of an ancient Cretan town/city, and I was thinking that both are cognate with Ancient Greek φαίος (“grey; any color mixed with black and white; harsh (of sound)”), a word has been compared with Latvian *gaišs* (“light, bright”) and Lithuanian *gaišas* (“beam of light, redness in the sky”), with φαίος and the Baltic words posited to derive from a reconstructed PIE **g^{wh}aiso-* (“bright, shining”), though there are formal issues with this. Other reconstructions which have been proposed are **phaiwós* and **phaiswós*.

I was not satisfied with “bright, shining” was the meaning of Hephaistos, so when I found those fever and moth words, I decided to go with that theory, and that is what I still favor.

Meanwhile, I notice that my previous (and unpublished) theory where Hephaistos is cognate with φαίος and the Baltic words, that theory was independently thought of by Sean Whalen (if not also by others), who published that hypothesis recently. I myself am not sure that φαίος even comes from the older meaning “bright”: the meaning “harsh” could indicate that, but it might not: since the skin of many sheep is grey (from light gray to dark grey to black; with some having white skin or pink skin), and we find a Latvian word *rupjš* which means “harsh, coarse, rough; tough, thick”, and the Latvian *rupjš* is thought to derive from PIE **Hrewp-* (“to pull, to tear, to break”): the semantic evolution is thought to have been probably “to pluck, to tear (e.g., wool, feathers)” > (adj.) “uneven, harsh” (skin, after removing wool, feathers) > “coarse, harsh.”

It may be that Phaistos, the name of the ancient Cretan city, referred to the rocky hill upon which the palace and city were built; or more likely, Phaistos meant “tough, rugged; strong” referring to the fact that Phaistos was a fortified city and palace, a palatial hill fortress.

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